

OPEN
ACCESS

Incidence of Airborne Spores in Context to Fungal Diseases on *Glycine max* L. (Soybean) from Niphad Tehsil of Nashik District, Maharashtra

MR Kapadi¹ and NB Pawar²

¹Department of Botany, KTHM College, Nashik

²Department of Botany, LVH Arts, Science & Commerce College, Panchavati, Nashik

Correspondence and requests should be addressed to MRK (email: nisha.rayate@gmail.com)

Abstract

Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) is one of the most important oilseed cash crops and the fastest growing crop in India as well as in the world due to its high productivity, profitability and vital contribution towards maintaining soil fertility. The present investigation was carried out over the Soyabean field during the Kharif season by using a Tilak air sampler. The correlation with environmental parameters and airborne fungal spores plays an important role in the seasonal development of many plant diseases. The present study reveals the actual disease incidence and prevalence of airborne pathogenic fungal spores were responsible for diseases on certain crops. Some of them are *Alternaria* leaf spot (*Alternaria*), Target Leaf Spot (*Corynespora cassiicola*), Frogeye leaf spot, (*Cercospora sojina*) and Anthracnose (*Colletotrichum*). The present study will be sustainable for agro-economy and beneficial for growers to enhance the current knowledge on identification and determining incidence levels of different diseases of a certain crop. Knowing the disease history of a field and keeping abreast of reported disease development during the growing season helps to protect yield potential.

Keywords: *Glycine max*; Tilak air sampler; Kharif season; Cash crop; Fungal spores

Introduction

An Incidence of airborne fungal diseases, can affect Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) production and different production constraints and reduce the quality and quantity. Aerobiology deals with the study of airborne fungal spores, pollen grains, bacteria, viruses, minute insects and molds, etc. The dissemination of fungal spores depends upon weather conditions and climatic factors. The correlation between meteorological parameters and fungal spores plays a pivotal role in the incidence of some fungal diseases in Soybean crops.

The most significant oil seed crop in the world is soybean, which supplies two-thirds of the world's protein needs as well as 25% of the edible oil. Around 85% of soybeans are processed each year into soy meal and oil. Approximately 98% of the soy meal is crushed and further processed into animal feed. The remainder is used to make industrial goods including fatty acids, soaps, and biodiesel. The major Soybean producing nation is the United States, Brazil, and Argentina, these three countries dominate global production and contribute 80% of the world's Soybean supply.

Received:
12-12-2022

Accepted:
30-12-2022

Published:
31-12-2022

The origin of Soybean at the beginning of China's agricultural age dated back 6000 years. It is most popular in China, Japan, Korea, the Philippines, Manchuria, and Indonesia, for centuries, like to be as meat, milk, cheese, bread, and oil. The reason should be, it has earned epithets like "Cow of the field" or "Gold from the soil". In India, Soybean is a major oilseed rainfed cash crop and contributes significantly to the Indian edible oil pool, established in the agro-ecosystem of central and peninsular India. The major soybean-growing states are Maharashtra mostly in the Marathwada region, Madhya Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Chhattisgarh, Meghalaya, Andhra Pradesh, Nagaland, Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, and West Bengal. In India, after cereals, oilseeds are the second-largest agricultural commodity and the fifth-largest vegetable oil economy in the world.

Soybean contributes to total oilseed production by 43% and 25% to the total oil production in the country and exporting soya meal earns foreign exchange. An account of 14% of the gross cropped area in the country only 50% requirement is complete and on-demand by importing 50% of its requirement. This research aims to enhance the production by efficient control of diseases and Soybean growing farmers by empowering them to be self-reliant in knowing the prevalence of diseases on which period of time and taking immediate action. This research reveals that these efforts were not beneficial merely in terms of productivity but to reduce their expenses and increase the economy. This research has been done in Niphad Tehsil of Nashik District. Recently, the state government announced that cluster projects are to be implemented in the district where cotton and soybean are cultivated as a Kharif crop by farmers.

Materials and methods

Sampling site

The present aeromycological investigation was conducted during 2021-2022 in the Kharif season over the Soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) crop in Niphad Tehsil of Nashik District, Maharashtra. In the present research, the airborne fungal spore trapping was done by using the Tilak Air Sampler (Tilak and Kulkarni; 1970) located in the middle of a two-acre field of Soybean. Monitoring of airborne fungal spores from sampling sites selected for investigation was carried out in the Kharif season from June to October in the Soybean field for five months.

Apparatus and its working

Samples were collected by operating a volumetric Tilak air sampler (Tilak and Kulkarni; 1970). Sampling was carried out by operating the air sampler continuously with its orifice projection tube kept at a constant height of 1 meter above ground level. The apparatus was protected from rain by a polythene cover, which does not impair the sampling efficiency. It consists cubical tin box, runs on an electric power supply and it will provide a continuous sampling of air for 8 days. Air will be sucked in (5 liters/minute) and impinges on the transparent cello tape of the rotating drum coated with a thin layer of petroleum jelly; thus, the bioparticles from the air will be entrapped. The exposed cello tape was changed every 8 days and cut into 16 equal parts; each representing 12 hours of trace area, of a day & night accordingly. The pieces of cello tape were mounted on microscopic slides using glycerine jelly as a mount.

The recognition of spore type is established by its (i) Morphological characters (ii) Visual identification by correlation with the reference slide prepared (iii) By uncovering the culture plate method. Attempts are made to recognize fungal spore type up to the generic level and when possible, up to the species level.

Scanning

The scanning of the collected sample was done regularly for two years. A total of 9600 sq. microns of the area was obtained during the daily scan by using 10x and 45x eyepieces of the compound microscope as well as a binocular microscope. Scanning of prepared glass slides was done regularly and identification of pathogenic fungal spores and other bio-particles was based on microscopic diagnostic features, reference slides, and available literature (Figure 1).

Corynespora

Colletotricum

Alternaria

Cercospora

Fig. 1 Spore photoplates

Fig. 2. Graph showing the correlation between meteorological parameters

Result and Discussion

In a further study, predicting the occurrence of fungal diseases and assessing the damage from the plant is correlated with environmental parameters that characterize patterns of distribution and abundance of the pest and pathogen in the Soybean field. Humid and warm climatic conditions are favourable for the incidence of many diseases (Figure 3). Some of them are *Alternaria leaf spots*, caused by the necrotrophic fungus *Alternaria alternata*. It affects the foliage, there will be dark, necrotic patches with concentric rings that will eventually consolidate into larger necrotic regions. Later in the season, infected leaves prematurely dry out and fall. Target Leaf Spot, caused by the fungus *Corynespora cassiicola*, lower leaves develop small brown specks that are round to irregular with a possible yellow halo. The mature spot may be 3/8 to 5/8 inches or more in diameter. Some may have a zonate appearance. Dark brown and range from specks to elongated lesions infected the stem and petiole. Lesions developing on pods are circular, usually small (1/32 inch), and purple with black and brown margins. This disease is favored by high humidity more than 80% or free moisture (Figure 2). Dry condition help suppress the disease. Frogeye leaf spot, caused by the fungus *Cercospora sojina*.

Fig. 3. Graph showing monthly concentration of spores

Symptoms occur on leaves with centers that become ash-gray to light-brown. Later, the lesions change from being angular to circular, with a dark-brown to purple border enclosing a tan to grey core. In the centre of lesions on the undersides of leaves, spore production may be seen as a dark, black spot. Favored by warm (77 to 86 °F) temperatures and prolonged periods of dew or light rain. Anthracnose, caused by the fungus *Colletotrichum truncatum*, brown to black, irregularly shaped lesions on stem, pods, and petioles. Premature defoliation can occur from petiole girdling. Infected pods may be filled with mycelium instead of seeds or seeds may be fewer and/or smaller and can also be brown, moldy, shriveled, or normal in appearance. Dark spines or setae appear within lesions. Vein necrosis can be seen between the main veins of rolling leaves. favours warm, rainy, and humid weather. Some infected seeds might not grow. Seedling damping off occurs when infected seedlings develop dark, sunken cankers on the cotyledons, epicotyl, and radicle.

A further microscopic study was undertaken to understand the incidence of airborne fungal spores infecting the soybean plant. Some diseases are recorded which are helpful to reduce the disease manifestation by management of crop rotation and tillage to encourage residue decomposition. It can help reduce pathogen levels. The correlation with environmental parameters is the most important basis for devising the disease forecasting system, for the efficient control of diseases of the Soybean crop.

Conclusion

The present aeromycological studies over the soybean field have contributed to understanding the components of the airspora in year 2021-22. It was observed that the occurrence of airborne fungal spores over the soybean field was in correlation with the weather changes, field operation, plant growth and disease incidence on the crop. Regarding the development and spreading of the disease, it can be said that plant disease generally does not occur unless certain requirements are fulfilled. First, there must be a host plant present in a vulnerable or susceptible condition. Second, there must be infective spores or vegetative parts of a pathogen on the host or in position to be quickly transferred to the host and third, the environmental conditions must be favourable for active invasion of the host plant by the pathogen. Conclusively, the occurrence of disease can be predicted by the relationship between weather and disease development.

References

- Ambhore JS (2015) Aeromycological studies over maize and paddy crops. Laxmi Book Publication, Solapur.
- Yorinori JT (1992) Management of Foliar Fungal Diseases in Soybean in Brazil. In: Copping, L.G., Green, M.B., Rees, R.T. (eds) Pest Management in Soybean. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-2870-4_18
- Ploper LD and Backman PA (1992) Nature and Management of Fungal Diseases Affecting Soybean Stems, Pods, and Seeds. In: Copping, L.G., Green, M.B., Rees, R.T. (eds) Pest Management in Soybean. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-2870-4_17
- Dhundiraj LS (2020) Basidiomycetes Spore Concentration Over Soybean Field. International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology 7 (3): 260-264.
- Rondon MN and Lawrence K (2021) The fungal pathogen *Corynespora cassiicola*: A review and insights for target spot management on cotton and Soya bean. Journal of phytopathology 169: 329-338.
- Mueller DS, Wise KA, Sisson AJ, et al. (2016) Corn Yield Loss Estimates Due to Diseases in the United States and Ontario, Canada from 2012 to 2015. Plant Health Prog 17: 211-222.
- Borah M (2019) Identification of Soybean Diseases in Assam. International Journal of Recent Scientific Research 10(8): 34154-34159.
- Tilak ST and Kulkarni RL (1970) A new air sampler. Experientia 26: 443-444.

Author Contributions

MRK and NBP conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

There is no funding source for the present study.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Citation: Kapadi MR and Pawar NB (2022) Incidence of Airborne Spores in Context to Fungal Diseases on *Glycine max* L. (Soybean) from Niphad Tehsil of Nashik District, Maharashtra. Environ Sci Arch 1 (STI-1): 64-69.